

THERMOMECHANICAL MODELLING THE FIRE PROPERTIES OF FIBRE-POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A concern with using fibre reinforced polymer composites is their high flammability and poor resistance to fire. When composites are exposed to fire the polymer matrix is thermally degraded which deteriorates the mechanical properties. Until recently the residual mechanical properties of composites following a fire were determined through empirical fire tests, and models for predicting the post-fire properties were not available. In this paper, simple-to-use models are presented for determining the residual tension, compression and flexural properties of burnt composites following a fire. The accuracy of the models is assessed for a variety of composite materials. Fire tests were performed on composites containing carbon, glass or Kevlar fibres with an epoxy, polyester, vinyl ester or phenolic resin matrix. These materials were exposed to a wide range of fire conditions with temperatures from 525 to 850°C for times up to 30 minutes. It is found that the post-fire properties drop rapidly with increasing heat flux and duration of the fire due to the thermal degradation of the composite to char. It is shown that the post-fire properties of burnt composites can be accurately determined using the models.

KEYWORDS: Polymer composites, fire, mechanical properties, modelling

INTRODUCTION

A concern with the use of fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites is their high flammability and poor fire resistance. Most composite materials ignite easily when exposed to a hot fire, and large amounts of heat, smoke and fumes are released. Due to the thermal decomposition of the polymer matrix, and in some cases the fibres, the mechanical properties of a composite can be severely degraded. Experimental fire studies by Pering et al. [1], Sorathia et al. [2] and Mouritz and colleagues [3-7] have shown that the residual mechanical properties of composites following a fire can be reduced considerably by decomposition and heat damage to the resin matrix. While these studies provide useful insights into the loss in stiffness and strength of composites due to fire, models for predicting the post-fire properties are needed to reduce the requirement for performing expensive and time-consuming fire tests.

Mouritz and Mathys [4,5] recently proposed simple-to-use analytical models to calculate the post-fire mechanical properties of burnt composites. The models can be used to determine the post-fire mechanical properties of composites at room temperature after the fire has been extinguished. (The models are not capable of predicting the mechanical properties of a burning composite during a fire). However, the accuracy of the models has only been assessed for a few types of woven glass fibre composites [3-7]. A more thorough assessment is needed to ensure the post-fire properties of any type of FRP composite can be calculated using the models.

The aim of this paper is to further validate models recently proposed by Mouritz and Mathys [4,5] for determining the post-fire tension, compression and flexure properties of burnt composite materials. The accuracy of the models is rigorously tested against a large amount of experimental mechanical property data for a wide variety of burnt thermoset matrix composites. The models are tested for composites reinforced with woven glass, chopped glass, Kevlar or carbon fibres and polyester, vinyl ester, epoxy or phenolic resin matrices. The models are also tested for composites burnt under different fire conditions.

POST-FIRE MECHANICAL PROPERTY MODELS

Basis of the Models

Mouritz and Mathys [3-5] have proposed analytical models to predict the post-fire mechanical properties of flat panels of single-skin composites that have been uniformly heated over one surface by fire, as illustrated in figure 1. The figure shows an idealised representation of the distribution of fire damage through a flat composite panel that is based on experimental observations by Mouritz and Mathys [3-5]. A partly burnt composite material can be simply considered to consist of two well-defined layers: (i) a thermally degraded region where the resin has been decomposed to a carbon-rich char, and (ii) an unburnt region that contains small delamination cracks close to the combustion front. In this study these two regions are called the 'char' and 'unburnt regions', respectively. Equations are presented for calculating the residual tension, compression and flexure properties of single-skin FRP composites at room temperature that have the fire damage profile shown in figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic showing the through-thickness distribution of fire damage in a composite.

A basic assumption of the models is that the mechanical properties of the char and unburnt regions can be combined using rule-of-mixtures analysis to obtain the bulk stiffness and strength of a fire-damaged composite. In the derivation of the models, a number of simplifying assumptions have been made about the nature of the fire damage and the affect of this damage on the mechanical properties of composites. The key assumptions are that the:

- (i) char region has a uniform thickness (defined as d_c in figure 1),
- (ii) tension, compression and flexure properties of the char are constant throughout the char region,
- (iii) tension, compression and flexure properties of the unburnt region are the same as the mechanical properties of the original (unburnt) composite, and
- (iv) mechanical properties of the unburnt region are constant throughout, and are not affected by excessive heating of the resin matrix or by the small delamination cracks.

Post-Fire Tension Stiffness and Strength

Mouritz and Mathys [4,5] suggest that when a burnt composite is loaded in uniaxial tension at room temperature then the residual tensile properties can be approximated using a rule-of-mixtures model. In the model the post-fire tensile properties are determined by combining the tensile properties of the unburnt and char regions using a rule-of-mixtures formulation to give the bulk stiffness and failure strength of the fire-damaged composite.

Mouritz and Mathys [4,5] propose that the tensile stiffness (S_t) of an evenly burnt composite (as shown in figure 1) can be estimated using the simple expression:

$$S_t = \left(\frac{d - d_c}{d} \right) S_o + \left(\frac{d_c}{d} \right) S_c \quad [1]$$

where d_c is the char thickness, d is the original thickness of the composite, and S_c and S_o are the tensile stiffness of the char and unburnt (original) material, respectively. The first term on the right-hand side of equation 1 represents the tensile stiffness of the unburnt region whereas the second term gives the stiffness of the char region.

Similarly, the tensile failure strength (σ_t) of a burnt composite can be determined by:

$$\sigma_t = \left(\frac{d - d_c}{d} \right) \sigma_{t(o)} + \left(\frac{d_c}{d} \right) \sigma_{t(c)} \quad [2]$$

where $\sigma_{t(c)}$ and $\sigma_{t(o)}$ are the tensile strengths of the char and unburnt composites.

Post-Fire Compression Stiffness and Buckling Strength

The model proposed by Mouritz and Mathys [4] to predict the compression stiffness and Euler buckling strength of a fire-damaged composite is also based on rule-of-mixtures. In this case the model combines the compression properties of the char and unburnt regions of the composite. The model for determining compression strength is governed by the failure mechanism of the burnt composite when loaded in axial compression, and in this paper the failure mode of Euler buckling is considered.

It is proposed that the uniaxial compression stiffness, S_c , of a fire-damaged composite in the form of a slender beam can be determined using:

$$S_c = \left(\frac{d - d_c}{d} \right) S_{c(o)} + \left(\frac{d_c}{d} \right) S_{c(c)} \quad [3]$$

where $S_{c(c)}$ and $S_{c(o)}$ are the compression stiffness of the char and unburnt composite.

When a slender composite beam is loaded in uniaxial compression then failure generally occurs by buckling. Mouritz and Mathys [4] have shown that when a slender beam is uniformly burnt then the Euler buckling load (P_c) is determined using a modified version of the well-known Euler buckling equation:

$$P_c \approx C\pi^2 E_{c(o)} b(d-d_c) \left[\frac{0.2887(d-d_c)}{L} \right]^2 \quad [4]$$

where $E_{c(o)}$ is the compression modulus of the unburnt composite in the load direction, L and b are the length and width of the beam, and C is the constant determined by the restraint conditions at the beam ends, and equals unity when the ends of the beam are simply supported. In equation 4 it is assumed that the compression strength of the char is negligible. Once P_c is determined, the Euler buckling strength of a fire-damaged composite beam (σ_c) is then calculated by:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P_c}{bd} \quad [5]$$

Post-Fire Flexural Modulus and Strength

The post-fire flexural modulus and strength of a uniformly burnt composite can also be determined using a rule-of-mixtures formulation that combines the flexural properties of the char and unburnt regions. Mouritz and Mathys [4,5] show that when a fire-damaged composite beam with a slender geometry is loaded in quarter-point bending then the apparent flexural modulus (E_f) can be determined using:

$$E_f = \left\{ \frac{4(d-d_n)^3 + 4(d_n-d_c)^3}{d^3} + 4 \frac{E_{f(c)}}{E_{f(o)}} \cdot \frac{[d_n^3 - (d_n-d_c)^3]}{d^3} \right\} E_{f(o)} \quad [6]$$

where $E_{f(c)}$ and $E_{f(o)}$ are the flexural modulus of the char and unburnt composite, respectively. d_n is the distance from the outer surface of the char region to the neutral stress axis of the beam, and is calculated using:

$$d_n = \frac{E_{f(o)}d^2 - d_c^2(E_{f(o)} - E_{f(c)})}{2E_{f(o)}d + 2E_{f(c)}d_c - 2E_{f(o)}d_c} \quad [7]$$

The flexural failure load (P_f) for a fire-damaged composite beam in quarter-point loading can be calculated using:

$$P_f = \frac{8}{L^*} \left\{ \frac{\sigma_{f(o)} \cdot b}{3} \cdot \frac{(d-d_n)^3 + (d_n-d_c)^3}{(d-d_n)} + \frac{\sigma_{f(o)} \cdot b}{3} \cdot \frac{E_{f(c)}}{E_{f(o)}} \cdot \frac{[d_n^3 - (d_n-d_c)^3]}{(d-d_n)} \right\} \quad [8]$$

where L^* is the length of the load span and $\sigma_{f(o)}$ is the flexural strength of the unburnt composite. Once P_f is calculated, then the apparent flexural strength of a burnt composite loaded in four-point bending is determined using:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3L_s P_f}{4bd} \quad [9]$$

where L_s is the length of the support span.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

A variety of burnt composites were examined to ensure the model was rigorously tested against a diverse range of post-fire mechanical property data. The composition and mechanical properties of the composites before fire testing are given in tables 1 & 2, respectively. The composites were made using the wet hand lay-up method with the exceptions of the woven carbon/epoxy prepreg composite that was manufactured using an autoclave and the woven carbon/epoxy composite made using vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding processes.

Table 1. FRP composite materials.

Composite	Lay-Up	Fibre Volume Content	Thickness (mm)
Woven glass/polyester	[0/90] _s	0.34	5.1 & 12.0
Chopped glass/polyester	Isotropic	0.17	5.5
Kevlar/polyester	[0/90] _s	0.86	4.4
Woven glass/vinyl ester	[0/90] _s	0.35	12.0
Woven glass/epoxy	[0/90] _s	0.33	7.4
Chopped glass/epoxy	Isotropic	0.14	6.7
Woven carbon/epoxy	[0/±45/90] _s	0.79	4.9
Carbon/epoxy prepreg	[0]	0.64	8.0
Carbon/epoxy prepreg	[0/90] _s	0.64	8.0
Carbon/epoxy prepreg	[0/±45/90] _s	0.64	8.0
Woven glass/phenolic	Isotropic	0.39	6.9 & 12.0
Chopped glass/phenolic	[0/90] _s	0.16	6.0
Kevlar/phenolic	[0/90] _s	0.59	5.9

Table 2. Mechanical properties of composites.

Composite	Tension		Compression		Flexure	
	Stiffness (x 10 ⁶ N/m)	Strength (MPa)	Stiffness (x 10 ⁶ N/m)	Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)
Woven glass/polyester	5.96	159	24.8	134	17.8	241
Chopped glass/polyester	2.57	94.3			10.5	159
Kevlar/polyester	4.31	353			11.4	130
Woven glass/vinyl ester	4.89	180			17.7	217
Woven glass/epoxy	4.11	178			12.9	212
Chopped glass/epoxy	2.62	93.0			10.0	172
Woven carbon/epoxy	8.94	524			55.8	1018
Carbon/epoxy [0]					91.0	1070
Carbon/epoxy [0/90] _s					64.5	774
Carbon/epoxy [0/±45/90] _s					49.8	696
Woven glass/phenolic	5.36	162			16.8	147
Chopped glass/phenolic	2.62	90.0			8.1	133
Kevlar/phenolic	4.31	350			11.4	92

Fire tests were performed on the composites using the radiant heater in the Stanton Redcroft cone calorimeter. In the fire test, a composite specimen was placed horizontal to the electric radiant heat source in the cone calorimeter and exposed to the incident heat flux of 50 kW/m^2 for times up to 30 minutes. A heat flux of 50 kW/m^2 was used as it represents the intensity of a medium-sized room fire. Thermocouples at the position of the exposed surface of the composites reached about 650°C . Some composites were also tested at heat fluxes of 25, 75 and 100 kW/m^2 that corresponded to temperatures of about 525, 750 and 850°C , respectively. After a fire test, the burning composite was removed from the cone calorimeter, the flames were extinguished, and the specimen was cooled to room temperature so that the residual mechanical properties could be measured.

The tensile stiffness and failure strength of the composites was measured according to the ASTM tensile test specification [8] using specimens that were 25 mm wide and with a gauge length of 100 mm. The tensile stiffness was determined instead of Young's modulus because of the difficulty in reliability measuring the strain in the burnt specimens using strain gauges or an extensometer. The tensile stiffness was taken to be the gradient of the linear (elastic) portion of the load against cross-head displacement curve (expressed in N/m).

Compression tests were performed at room temperature on slender composite beams that were 150 mm long and 25 mm wide. The ends of the beams were simply supported between thick steel platens during testing. The compression stiffness of the composite was determined by the slope of the applied load versus cross-head displacement curve in the linear (elastic) region. The Euler buckling strength was taken to be the applied stress at which the specimen began to buckle. Compression tests were only performed on the woven glass/polyester composite.

The flexural modulus and strength of the burnt composites were determined at room temperature using the ASTM four-point bend test [9]. The specimens were 240 mm long and 25 mm wide, and were loaded at a cross-head speed of 5 mm/min in $\frac{1}{4}$ -point loading under failure. The flexural tests were performed with the burnt surface placed against the two load points so it experienced bending-induced compression. The tension, compression and flexural properties were measured using at least four specimens burnt under the same fire condition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of all the FRP composites decreased after fire exposure. Typical examples of the reduction to the tensile strength of composites with increasing heating time and heat flux are given in figure 2. Similar reductions to the mechanical properties were measured for the other composite materials. The reduction to the post-fire mechanical properties is due mostly to thermal decomposition and combustion of the polymer matrix. When exposed to the extreme heat inside the cone calorimeter, a char layer formed in all the composite materials due to thermal degradation of the polymer matrix. The profile of the char layer in a burnt composite is shown in figure 3, and it is seen that the thickness of the char layer is constant through the material. The char layer has the same profile as the char region shown in figure 1 that is used as the basis for deriving the post-fire mechanical property models. The thickness of the char layer in burnt composites can be easily measured in a number of ways, including visually and by ultrasonics, and as expected it was found that the char thickness increased with heating time and heat flux. The growth of the char layer is responsible for the reduction to the mechanical properties of the composites shown in figure 2 because char has very low stiffness and strength.

Figure 2. Post-fire tensile strengths of composites following exposure to fire for increasing (a) time and (b) heat flux. (The fire tests were performed at (a) a constant heat flux of 50 kW/m² and (b) constant heating time of 325 seconds). The curves show the theoretical reduction to the post-fire tensile strength.

Figure 3. Profile of fire damage through a burnt composite. The horizontal line indicates the boundary between the char and unburnt regions.

Mechanical tests performed on fully charred composites by Mouritz and Mathys [3-5] revealed that the stiffness and strength of the char is usually negligible compared to the original mechanical properties for most composites. Typically the mechanical properties of the char are 0-10% and 8-20% of the compressive and tensile properties, respectively. However to examine further simplification of the models in this study, the mechanical properties of the char were taken to be zero in the determination of the theoretical post-fire properties.

The curves in figure 2 show the theoretical reduction to the mechanical properties with increased heating time and heat flux that were calculated using the post-fire models. It is evident that there is excellent agreement with the theoretical and measured post-fire properties when the char is assumed to have negligible properties. The data required to determine the post-fire mechanical properties using the models are the original stiffness/modulus and strength of the unburnt composite and the char thickness.

The theoretical post-fire tension, compression and flexure strengths are compared against the experimental post-fire property data for all of the composites in figure 4. Data is shown for the composites tested at the different heating times and heat fluxes. The straight line in the figures has a slope of unity, and therefore the closer the data points are to the line the better is the agreement between the theoretical and measured post-fire properties. With the exception of a few

out-lying data points, the results are clustered close to the line indicating good agreement between theory and experiment. Similar agreement is found between the theoretical and measured post-fire elastic modulus values for the burnt composites. Table 3 shows the correlation coefficients (R) between the calculated and measured post-fire properties, and the agreement is good in all cases. This reveals that the post-fire mechanical properties of FRP composites can be accurately determined using the models.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4. Comparison of the theoretical and experimental (a) post-fire tension, (b) post-fire compression and (c) post-fire flexural strengths of the composites. The insert in (c) shows in greater detail the comparison at relatively low flexural strength values.

Table 3. Correlation coefficients (R) between the theoretical and experimental post-fire mechanical properties.

<i>Post-Fire Property</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>Sample Population</i>
Tensile stiffness	0.77	73
Tensile strength	0.93	73
Compressive stiffness	0.96	12
Compressive strength	0.90	15
Flexural modulus	0.95	96
Flexural strength	0.88	80

The good agreement between the theory and experiment also indicates that the char is the dominant type of fire damage that degrades the mechanical properties. The models do not account for the potential loss in stiffness and strength due to other types of fire-induced damage, such as excessive heating of the polymer matrix or delamination cracks in the unburnt portion of the composite. Despite not considering these types of damage, the models are still accurate which indicates that the char is mostly responsible for the reduction to the post-fire properties.

CONCLUSIONS

The post-fire tension, compression and flexure properties of fibre reinforced thermoset composites decreased after fire exposure. The reduction was mainly due to the formation of char from the thermal degradation and combustion of the polymer matrix. It appears that other types of fire-induced damage, such as delamination cracking and overheating of the resin within the unburnt region of the composite, do not have a large influence on the post-fire mechanical properties. The post-fire properties of uniformly burnt composites can be determined using simple-to-use models that are based on rule-of-mixtures analysis. The only data required to calculate the post-fire properties using the models is the original mechanical properties of the

composite and the char thickness. The models were validated using a large amount of mechanical property data for a wide range of engineering composite materials that had been exposed for different heat fluxes and times. It was found that in most cases the post-fire mechanical properties can be accurately determined using the models.

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